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Advancing Solvent-based CO₂ Capture: Integrated Modeling of Packing and Casing Cavity Section in Rotating Packed Beds

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Abstract

Rotating Packed Beds (RPBs) are poised to replace conventional Packed Bed (PB) towers, advancing solvent-based CO₂ capture through intensified mass transfer processes. Effective modeling is crucial for understanding these intensified phenomena and complex liquid flow patterns during CO₂ absorption in RPB reactors. While the cavity section—located between the packing and the casing—plays a significant role in overall capture efficiency, it is often overlooked in existing models that primarily focus on the packing section. In the cavity section, the liquid flows as droplets and forms a film along the casing wall. This work addresses this gap by integrating two distinct mass transfer methodologies, each adapted to the liquid flow variations in both the packing and cavity sections. The proposed integrated absorption model captures all critical phenomena along the radial dimension, offering a comprehensive simulation of RPB performance. The methodology builds on an existing rate-based, steady-state framework from our previous work, while incorporate a semi-empirical approach to predict mass transfer in the cavity section. A custom model for the packing section uses the shooting method to solve material and energy balance equations, focusing on a monoethanolamine (MEA) solution. The model was validated using up-to-date experimental data for a 30 wt.% MEA solution in a RPB absorber across twenty different tests, considering various conditions such as rotational speed, liquid-to-gas ratio, and lean loading. The predicted outlet gas CO₂ mole fraction aligned closely with experimental results, showing a mean absolute deviation of 4%. Additionally, the simulation enabled detailed analysis of key gas and liquid phenomena along the radial dimension, such as variations in gas phase CO₂ molar flow rate and liquid temperature. Notably, the cavity section enhanced capture efficiency, particularly near the inner casing wall where droplets accumulate to form a film.

Keywords: process intensification; rotating packed bed; post-combustion CO₂ capture; amine-based; mass transfer modeling.

Nomenclature

A	surface area (m ²)
a _c	centrifugal acceleration (m/s ²)
a _{gl}	effective gas-liquid interfacial area (m ² /m ³)
a _p	specific surface area of packing (m ² /m ³)
d	average droplet diameter (m)
d _h	hydraulic diameter (m)
E ₀	standard kinetic energy (J)

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g	acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2)
P	gas pressure (kPa)
Q	liquid flow rate (m^3/s)
R	radius (m)
t_{res}	residence time in the cavity section (s)
T	temperature (K)
u	velocity (m/s)
u_0	initial velocity (m/s)
Z_p	axial length of packing (m)

Greek symbols

ε	void fraction of the packing (-)
μ	dynamic viscosity ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)
ν	kinematic viscosity (m^2/s)
ω	angular velocity (rad/s)
ρ	density (kg/m^3)
σ	surface tension (N/m)

Subscripts

c	casing
cf	inner wall casing film
d	droplets
f	film
g	gas phase
l	liquid phase
o	outer packing
p	packing
r	radial dimension

Dimensionless numbers

Re	Reynolds
We	Weber

1. Introduction

Post combustion CO_2 capture technologies (PCC) are at the forefront of research and investment efforts, to combat global warming through emissions reduction. Among these technologies, Rotating Packed Beds (RPB) emerge as a promising solution for amine solvent-based CO_2 capture [1]. RPBs are utilized in chemical absorption and regeneration processes. The rotational motion generates high centrifugal forces that intensify the associated phenomena. This intensification, combined with the appropriate solvent, can reduce the equipment size by 10x times compared to traditional packed bed towers [2]. As the demand for scaling these systems to meet industrial CO_2 capture requirements grows, RPBs offer a compelling solution by reducing the size and cost of equipment while maintaining efficiency.

In general, RPB are divided into two main sections: the packing section, where most of the mass transfer occurs, and the cavity section. The latter contributes to CO_2 capture and works in coordination with the packing section [3]. Research has shown that the cavity section contributes approximately 15-26% of the total mass transfer in RPBs, depending on operating conditions [4]. Therefore, it has the potential to improve the overall capture efficiency while allowing for a more compact design. Process modeling serves as a crucial tool for predicting the performance of RPBs at industrial scales, providing a deeper understanding of the intensified phenomena and liquid flow distribution [5]. However, the rotational motion of RPBs introduces challenges in modeling the inherent non-linearity of liquid flow

distribution, which is critical for optimizing the design. Despite progress in RPB modeling, many existing studies primarily focus on the packing section while neglecting the effects of the outer cavity section [6, 7, 8]. There is a notable lack of studies investigating the behavior of critical parameters along the radial dimension. This gap is particularly evident when analyzing mass and heat transfer phenomena alongside gas pressure drop. Additionally, most common models approach the RPB as a black box, limiting the availability of detailed results within the RPB reactor. For instance, the model in [4] considered the cavity section but assumed isothermal operation and neglected the impact of pressure drop. Zhang et al. [9] present valuable results for RPB-based chemical absorption of CO₂ using an Eulerian porous medium approach. Their work offers a feasible model through Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis, which can be computationally intensive.

This work addresses the identified research gaps by integrating two distinct mass transfer methodologies, each designed to accommodate variations in liquid flow patterns. Unlike previous works, this integrated absorption model captures all critical phenomena simultaneously along the radial dimension. The proposed methodology combines the existing rate-based, steady-state framework from our previous RPB absorption modeling with a new approach that incorporates the cavity section. A custom model built in MATLAB has been developed for the packing section, grounded in first principles. It offers the advantages of detailed and flexible modeling, with simulation times reduced to just a few seconds. This model uses the shooting method to solve material and energy balance equations, specifically targeting a monoethanolamine (MEA) solution [10]. For the cavity section, the model adopts a semi-empirical mathematical approach to predict the total mass transfer area, accounting for both droplets and the film on the casing wall of a RPB [11]. The goal of this work is to present a comprehensive model that captures the phenomena occurring in both the packing and cavity sections, offering more precise predictions and deeper insights, thereby facilitating the scale-up of this technology for industrial applications.

2. Methods

The CO₂ absorption process within the RPB reactor is illustrated in Fig. 1. Gas and liquid phases flow in counter-current directions to intensify mass transfer rates [12]. The liquid flow enters the RPB through the distributors, contacting the inner packing section. It then flows radially through the packing until it reaches the outer packing radius, where it breaks into liquid droplets. These droplets accumulate, forming a film on the inner casing wall. The gas phase flows in the opposite direction and interacts with the liquid at each section of the reactor.

Fig. 1: Gas and liquid flow patterns within the RPB reactor.

Equations of mass and energy balance are valid for both the packing and the cavity section. These fundamental equations describe the corresponding phenomena and their respective interactions during CO₂ absorption. Our previous work on RPB-based absorption modeling describes in detail the process based on ordinary differential equations (ODE) for gas and liquid phase. A pressure drop equation was also included for a more holistic description of the process. The model incorporates a steady-state approach and uses the shooting method to solve these ordinary differential equations. The two-film theory is utilized to predict the mass transfer behavior of the process in the packing section. Although the fundamental equations for the cavity section remain unchanged, the transition in liquid flow

patterns is the primary factor that distinguishes the mass transfer methodology. The model employs a semi-empirical method to account for both mass transfer and hydrodynamic parameters based on experimental data [13].

2.1 Mass transfer

The employed mass transfer approach relies on three critical parameters within a RPB reactor: gas-liquid interfacial area, liquid phase mass transfer coefficient and gas phase mass transfer coefficient. The gas-liquid interfacial area plays a key role in quantifying the interaction between the two phases. It depends on the flow patterns and describes the ratio of mass transfer area to the respective volume of each section. For the packing section, the model incorporates a correlation for the interfacial area that accounts for centrifugal acceleration, along with thermodynamic and transport properties [14]. This correlation is presented below:

$$\frac{a_{gl_packing}}{a_p} = 1.5(a_p d_h)^{-0.5} \left(\frac{\rho_l u_l d_h}{\mu_l} \right)^{-0.2} \left(\frac{\rho_l u_l^2 d_h}{\sigma_l} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{u_l^2}{a_c d_h} \right)^{-0.45} \quad (1)$$

The cavity section is divided into two sub-sections: one containing droplets and the other consisting of the liquid film on the inner casing wall. The gas-liquid interfacial area for the cavity section is defined as:

$$a_{gl_cavity} = \frac{A_d + A_{cf}}{\pi(R_c^2 - R_o^2)Z_p} \quad (2)$$

where the effective axial length of the cavity section approximates the packing's axial length, as the main area responsible for mass transfer. The calculations that pertain to the mass transfer area of each flow are:

$$A_d = \frac{6 Q t_{res}}{d_c} \quad (3)$$

$$A_{cf} = \frac{\rho_l Q t_{res} \pi Z_p u_r^2}{E_0} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{res} = \frac{(R_c^2 - R_o^2)}{u_r} \quad (5)$$

where residence time refers to the time a droplet takes to travel from the outer packing radius to the inner wall of the casing. Gas and liquid phase mass transfer coefficients for the cavity section are calculated as noted in [4], while those for the packing section are derived from our previous work [10]. The interaction between gas and liquid flow in the cavity is similar to that of a spray column, due to the increased droplet velocity. Consequently, the mass transfer coefficients are the same as those in a spray column, including the estimated average droplet diameter.

2.2 Hydrodynamic parameters

Hydrodynamic parameters, including the average droplet diameter, the average radial velocity of droplets, and the gas pressure drop, are estimated using the following equations:

$$\frac{d_c}{R_o} = 0.042 W e^{-0.272} Re^{0.068} \left(\frac{u_o}{\omega R_o} \right)^{0.098} \left(\frac{R_o}{R_c} \right)^{-0.776} \quad (6)$$

$$u_r = 0.123 \omega^{1.113} R_o^{0.552} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = \rho_g \omega^2 r + \rho_g u_g \frac{du}{dr} \quad (8)$$

The average droplet diameter accounts for various operating conditions and the liquid's physical properties in the cavity zone of the RPB. Additionally, the correlation for average droplet velocity is fitted as a function of rotational speed and outer packing radius [13]. Finally, the pressure drop equation considers the centrifugal acceleration and Bernoulli's principle, and it has been modified to exclude friction losses within the packing material.

3. Model Validation

The integrated model was validated using the latest experimental data for a 30 wt.% aqueous MEA solution in an RPB absorber [15]. The experimental unit had an inner packing diameter of 8 cm, an axial packing length of 2 cm, an outer packing diameter of 30 cm, and an inner casing wall diameter of 36 cm. Expamet packing was used, providing a specific surface area of 663 m²/m³ and a void fraction of 0.801. The experimental setup employed synthetic flue gas containing 12 vol% CO₂ at 40°C. A total of 20 cases were tested under various conditions, including variations in rotational speed, liquid-to-gas ratio, and lean loading, among other factors. The model's evaluation centered on the outlet gas CO₂ mole fraction as a key indicator of the absorption process. As shown in Fig. 2, the predicted results for the outlet gas CO₂ mole fraction closely matched the experimental data, with a mean absolute deviation of 4%. These validation results demonstrate the model's robustness and sensitivity to different operational conditions.

Fig. 2: Comparison of predictive versus experimental results.

4. Results and Discussion

Absorption results are presented in terms of CO₂ gas flow rate and liquid temperature to simulate mass and energy behavior. Based on experimental conditions, the following figures illustrate the process behavior within the RPB reactor for both the packing and cavity sections. Initially, the gas-phase molar flow rate of CO₂ highlights the absorption process, starting from the outer radius where the feed gas enters the RPB (Fig. 3). In this region, droplets coalesce on the casing to form a film, leading to increased capture efficiency. As the gas flows into the cavity zone where droplet formation occurs, a reduction in the gas-liquid interfacial area is observed due to the increased volume. In the packing section, a steep gradient in CO₂ flow rate appears at the outer packing radius, where CO₂ fraction remains high. This gradient gradually decreases toward the inner radius due to reduced CO₂ fraction and lower temperature of the lean solution.

Fig. 3: Absorption profile of the CO₂ molar flow rate along the RPB radius.

Fig. 4 illustrates the liquid-phase temperature profile along the radial dimension. The liquid enters the RPB at the inner radius and moves outward the outer radius. This temperature profile mirrors the absorption pattern, reflecting the heat generated by the exothermic MEA-CO₂ reaction in the liquid phase, mostly in the packing section. The resulting temperature increase affects the thermophysical properties, the reaction kinetics and equilibrium pressure correlations. Thus, the temperature profile plays a key role in the process. Both figures that describe the process within the RPB have the same trend as the ones noted in [9], and highlight the model's ability to provide detailed simulations for each section of the RPB absorber.

Fig. 4: Liquid temperature variation along the RPB radius.

5. Conclusions

This work presented an integrated mathematical model for CO₂ absorption in RPBs. The model incorporates mass transfer methodologies that account for variations in liquid flow within the RPB reactor. Each liquid flow pattern—whether as a liquid film or droplets—was transformed into appropriate mathematical estimations to capture the absorption effects in both the packing and cavity sections. The model was validated by comparing simulated results with 20 different experimental data sets, yielding a mean absolute deviation of 4%. Simulation results of the gas-phase molar flow rate of CO₂ and the corresponding liquid temperature demonstrate the model's ability to capture critical phenomena within the RPB reactor. Furthermore, the absorption process reveals that the liquid film formed by accumulated droplets on the inner casing wall plays a significant role in overall CO₂ capture, exhibiting a gradient comparable to that of the packing section. This indicates that, in addition to the packing, a secondary section contributes to CO₂ absorption and has the potential to influence the design of scaled-up RPB units.

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